

METHODS OF DEVELOPING INDEPENDENT LEARNING ACTIVITIES IN MUSIC EDUCATION

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Abstract: This article analyzes effective methods for organizing and developing independent learning activities of students and pupils in the process of music education. Independent learning is considered an integral part of the modern education system, and its importance in the formation of musical competencies, the development of creative thinking, preparation for practical training and ensuring creative independence is highlighted.

Keywords: music education, interactive methods, creative activity, musical competence, self-assessment, methodological approach, music theory, performance.

Introduction.

In the context of the development of the modern education system, the development of independent learning activities in pupils and students is emerging as an important pedagogical problem. In particular, the field of music education is distinguished from other disciplines by its aesthetic, emotional and creative characteristics, which in turn requires the organization of the educational process based on person-oriented, active, reflective and creative methods. From this point of view, the development of independent learning activities in music disciplines is a complex process that serves not only to increase the efficiency of the educational process, but also to form musical thinking, artistic and aesthetic taste, analytical thinking and performing skills in students. The constructivist approach to education, metacognitive strategies, differential and individual teaching methods determine the theoretical and methodological foundations of the organization of independent learning in music disciplines. The process of independent learning transforms the student from a ready-made receiver of knowledge into an active knowledge-seeking and creative subject. In particular, the formation of skills for independent work in instrumental performance, solfeggio, composition, musical literacy, choral and ensemble classes is considered a decisive factor in ensuring the professional competence of students.

Today, digital educational technologies, online platforms, virtual simulators and interactive audio-visual resources serve as important tools for the independent mastery of musical knowledge. At the same time, by creating a motivational environment in the organization of independent learning, introducing self-assessment and reflection mechanisms, students will have the

opportunity to control the level of mastery. This article analyzes pedagogical approaches, methods and tools that are effective in this direction and reveals their practical significance in music education. The relevance of the research stems from the need for methodological approaches based on independent learning in the process of educating a creative, free-thinking, culturally and musically conscious young generation in the context of the orientation of education to the individual.

Methodology:

Determining the methodological foundations of the formation and development of independent learning activities in music education requires, first of all, a deep analysis of the nature of this process. The independent learning process is the student's acquisition of his own knowledge, skills and competencies without the direct assistance of a teacher, but in a didactically correct manner. This activity requires specific methodological approaches in the context of music education, since in this area knowledge is formed not only theoretically, but also practically, emotionally and aesthetically. The research methodology is based on a person-centered approach, activity-based learning, constructivist didactics, and the principle of creative mastery. These approaches serve to develop students' competencies such as self-awareness, independent formation of their own knowledge and means of musical expression, and a critical approach to the studied material.

Also, methods such as pedagogical diagnostics, monitoring, observation, portfolio-based assessment, and experimental analysis were selected as methodological foundations. These methods allow for the measurement, analysis, and evaluation of students' independent performance within the framework of music studies. In particular, in practical classes, independent performance analysis, observation, and qualitative analytical approaches in the process of creating one's own composition or interpreting works will have a methodological basis.

Among the methodological approaches, interactive teaching technologies (for example: "Case-study", "Brainstorming", "Portfolio", "Musical diary", "Flipped learning") are of particular importance. These technologies allow for independent study of musical material, its analysis, deep understanding, and enrichment with one's own creative thinking. For example, "Musical diary" - a student writes down his thoughts about the works he is studying independently every day, which forms emotional reflection and deepens musical thinking. At the same time, the methodology analyzed the use of digital technologies, in particular, music learning applications, online lesson platforms, audiovisual resources, and interactive notation programs. They act as a means of strengthening independent learning and allow students to learn at their own pace, in accordance with their personal needs. In general, the research methodology includes a combination of theoretical and practical approaches that serve to systematically, consistently, and gradually study the process of

independent learning in music education. This is manifested as a key factor in ensuring the internal activity, intellectual and creative development of the student in music education.

Literature analysis:

Theoretical and practical research on the formation and development of independent learning activities in music education has been widely covered in the pedagogical, psychological and music-educational research of many scientists. According to the results of the analysis, the methodological foundations of independent learning, pedagogical conditions, the content of educational materials and the psychological preparation of students are considered important factors determining its effectiveness.

In the 21st century, T. V. Alekseeva, O. G. Radionova[7; 336], I. A. Zimnyaya[8; 64], G. K. Selevko[4; 256], didactic approaches to independent learning have been developed by modern educators, such as A. Azamov[1; 180], Z. Mamarasulova[3; 154], M. Jorayev[2; 48], and R. Orinboyeva, who have demonstrated in their works the role, methodological aspects, and effectiveness of independent learning activities in the national education system. In particular, the educational model based on the "competence approach" put forward by Azamov also serves as a flexible platform for music education.

In the literature on the integration of digital technologies into education, in particular, E. Polat[5; 272], N. V. Matveeva[6; 198], S. A. Lavrentyeva have developed conceptual foundations for organizing independent learning using digital tools. These literatures highlight the practical possibilities of platforms such as Moodle, Google Classroom, Noteflight, MusicTheory.net as important tools for increasing student activity in the process of musical learning. The analyzed literature serves to scientifically substantiate the theoretical foundations, didactic modeling, interactive methods and technological tools necessary for the development of independent learning activities in music education. Based on these sources, it is possible to update the content of modern music education and organize activities aimed at self-development of students.

Discussion:

Independent learning activity in music education is not only the independent acquisition of knowledge, but also an important factor in the formation of personal musical thinking, strengthening the creative approach and developing aesthetic taste. However, the effective organization of this process does not happen by itself, but is carried out by the teacher through a carefully planned methodological approach, psychological support and modern technological tools. During the discussion, it was found that a set of several important conditions is necessary to increase the activity of independent learning.

First, the student must have internal motivation for independent learning and self-management competencies. In this case, the teacher's role is not only as a provider of knowledge, but also as a guide, facilitator (creator of a favorable

environment), and methodological consultant. By providing the student or student with musical works, performance styles, and educational materials that can be studied on the basis of free choice, they are given the opportunity to form an individual educational trajectory. Secondly, modern music education should be enriched with pedagogical technologies that serve independent learning activities. In particular, through the "Flipped learning" model, the student will have the opportunity to independently master theoretical materials outside of class, and discuss, analyze, and improve his performance during practical training. In addition, the methods of "Peer-assessment" and "Self-reflection" teach the student to analyze his own work, which serves creative musical growth.

Thirdly, experience shows that the correct selection and integration of digital tools is very important for the effective organization of independent learning. For example, through platforms such as Noteflight, MusicTheory.net, EarMaster, the student has the opportunity to independently test and develop his musical hearing, rhythm and theoretical knowledge. Also, evaluating his own performance based on video analysis (for example, recording and analyzing his own performance) forms metacognitive thinking in the student.

Conclusion.

Some difficulties are also observed in current practice. In particular, the low level of self-motivation of students, insufficient development of independent learning strategies, and methodological systematization of educational materials have a negative impact on the effectiveness of independent learning. Also, in some cases, it is observed that teachers are unable to fully integrate digital technologies into the educational process. Therefore, an integrated approach to the development of independent learning in music education is of great importance - that is, ensuring continuity between the student, teacher, and learning environment. As a result of this continuity, musical educational processes become an independent educational model that does not depend only on the teacher, but also shows the student's personal musical growth path.

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